

April 30, 2019

Marketing issues with Tomato and Onion Value addition: A Case study of Shikarpur District

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ **Dr.Faiz Muhammad Shaikh**-Associate Professor, SZABAC-Dokri

⁽²⁾ **Dr.Sultan Ahmed Maitlo**-Associate Professor, SZABAC-Dokri

⁽³⁾ **Dr.Javed Shabbir Dar**-Assistant Profesor- SZABAC-Dokri

Abstract:

Value addition in agriculture predominantly offers a means to increase, rejuvenate and stabilize farm income. The study carries out in Madhiji District Shikarpur. This survey was conducted using a questionnaire, where 60 household heads and 300 customers were sampled and interviewed, the main Objectives of study was to Specifically, this study focused on the impact of training provided to farmers on their perceived knowledge, acquisition of skills and adoption level of value added practices. Customer response analysis of tomato and onion Value Addition in Madhiji Shikarpur Sindh. A structural questionnaire was developed for the reliability and validity of data. The study recommends the policy should emphasize: increasing agricultural and post-harvest knowledge content in formal education, developing and manifesting a positive attitude and improving skills of potential producers, as well as improving producer's access to resources.

Key Words: Marketing issues, Tomato and Onion Value addition

Introduction:

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) is one of the most important vegetables worldwide. As it is a relatively short duration crop and gives a high yield, it is economically attractive, and the area under cultivation is increasing. Tomato belongs to the *Solanaceae* family. Tomatoes contribute to a healthy, well-balanced diet. They are rich in minerals, vitamins, essential amino acids, sugars, and dietary fibers. Tomato contains vitamin B and C, iron and phosphorus. Tomato fruits are consumed fresh in salads or cooked in sauces, soup and meat or fish dishes. They can be processed into purées, juices, and ketchup. Canned and dried tomatoes are economically important processed products. Yellow tomatoes have higher vitamin A content than red tomatoes, but red tomatoes contain lycopene, an antioxidant that may contribute to protection against carcinogenic substances.

Thanks to bumper crop in Sindh, the price of tomatoes has fallen up to Rs.2 per kg – but in big cities, the same vegetable is sold at an exorbitant rate of Rs60 per kg.

Sindh witnessed a bumper crop of tomatoes this year. The excess supply not only pushed down the price but shy away from the buyers also. Madhji a small farmer of Shikarpur district- who harvests tomatoes in his six-acre family land – is worried. After investing around Rs 40,000 per acre in farm inputs, his crop is not even paying back half of his investment. One acre yields around 100-120 mound tomatoes.

Onion is one of the important ingredients used in daily meals all over Pakistan. Onions are used in soups, salads, sauces and for seasoning foods. Onions as a part of the diet may play a part in preventing heart disease and other ailments (suggested by medical research). It is rich in phosphorus, calcium, and carbohydrates. The green leaves and immature and mature bulbs are eaten raw or used in the preparation of vegetables. Onions are used in soups, sauces and for seasoning foods. The small bulbs one pickled in vinegar. Recent research has suggested that onions in the diet may play a part in preventing heart disease and other ailments. Onion bulb is rich in phosphorus, calcium, and carbohydrates. The pungency in onion is due to a volatile oil known as an allyl-propyl disulphide. Onion is an important crop all over the world. In Pakistan, the major growing areas are, Awaran, Mastung, Kalat, Chagi, Khuzdar, and Turbat in Balochistan Hyderabad, Mirpurkhas, Sanghar, Sukkar,

April 30, 2019

Naushero Feroze and Badin in Sindh, Swat in KPK and Kasur, Gujranwala, Sheikhpura, Vehari, Khaniwal, D.G. Khan, and Jhang in Punjab. More than 50 percent of the total production comes from seven districts, namely Awaran, Mastung, Kalat, Turbat, Hyderabad, Mirpurkhas, Sanghar and Swat, (GOB, 2014).

Onion is a famous spice commodity grown all over the world and consumed in the various forms. Onion is a major ingredient in Pakistani food and commodity is typically cultivated a year thrice in monsoon, winter, and summer. Onion adds taste and flavor to food, and hence it is invariably used in several cuisines and culinary preparations. Onion possesses good medicinal values and is recommended on the medical ground also. Onion is processed in various products such as ketchup, chutney, sauce, puree, salsa, dry soup mixture, etc. A global review of area and production of onion shows that it is grown in 126 countries over an area of 2.3 million hectares producing 40.0 million tones of dry onion. Sixty-two percent of the world's production is from Asiatic countries. In Pakistan, during 2011-2012, the onion was cultivated on an area of 125.6 thousand hectares with a production of 1640 thousand tons showing 15.4 percent reduction in production over the preceding year 2010-2011 when the onion was cultivated on an area of 147.6 thousand hectares with a production of 1939.6 thousand tons (GOP, 2012).

Literature Review

The value chain methodology is a tradition developed from two strains of literature: the business literature on strategy and organization of Porter (1990) Porter, M. (1990). *The competitive advantage of nations*. New York, NY: Free Press. [Crossref], [Google Scholar] and the literature of global commodity chains promoted by Gereffi (1994, 1999) Gereffi, G. (1994). The organization of buyer-driven global commodity chains: How US retailers shape overseas production networks. In G. Gereffi & M. Korzeniewicz (Eds.), *Commodity chains and global capitalism* (pp. 95–122). Westport, CT: Praeger.

Gereffi, G. (1999). International trade and industrial upgrading in the apparel commodity chain. *Journal of International Economics*, 48, 37–70. 10.1016/S0022-1996(98)00075-0), Gereffi, Humphrey, and Sturgeon (2005) Gereffi, G., Humphrey, J., & Sturgeon, T. (2005). The governance of global value chains. *Review of International Political Economy*, 12, 78–104. 10.1080/09692290500049805 [Taylor & Francis Online], [Web of Science ®], [Google Scholar], Gereffi and Kaplinsky (2001) Gereffi, G., & Kaplinsky, R. (Eds.). (2001). *The value of value chains* (Vol. 32, No. 3). Brighton: IDS Bulletin. ISSN: 0265 5012 [Google Scholar], Gereffi and Korzeniewicz (1994) Gereffi, G., & Korzeniewicz, M. (Eds.). (1994). *Commodity chains and global capitalism*. Westport, CT: Praeger. [Google Scholar], Gereffi and Memodovic (2003) Gereffi, G., & Memodovic, O. (2003). *The global apparel value chain: What prospects for upgrading by developing countries?* (Sectoral Studies Series). United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO). Retrieved from <http://www.unido.org/doc/12218> [Google Scholar] and developed in numerous studies in the late 1990s. Agricultural value chains link urban consumption with rural production. Changing demand, as a consequence of urbanization, emergence of modern consumption patterns, or new trends in international trade, impacts on rural areas along value chains and spills over to marketing and production systems (Höffler & Maingi, 2005) Höffler, H., & Maingi, G. (2005). *Promotion of private sector development in agriculture (PSDA)*. Nairobi: GTZ – German Technical Cooperation. [Google Scholar]. Value chain analysis (VCA) has gained considerable importance in recent years. Although many definitions are applied, value chains essentially represent enterprises in which different producers and marketing companies work within their respective businesses to pursue one or more end-markets. The “value chain” is defined by Kaplinsky as “the full range of activities which are required to bring a product or service from conception, through the intermediary phases of production, delivery to final consumers, and final disposal after use” (Kaplinsky, 2000) Kaplinsky, R. (2000). Globalisation and unequalisation: What can be learned from value chain analysis? *Journal of Development Studies*, 37, 117–146. 10.1080/713600071 [Taylor & Francis Online], [Web of

April 30, 2019

Science @], [Google Scholar]). United Nations Industrial Development Organization (2009) United Nations Industrial Development Organization. (2009). *Agro-value chain analysis and development* (The UNIDO Approach, A Staff Working Paper). Vienna. [Google Scholar]) describes it as the entire range of activities undertaken to bring a product from the initial input-supply stage, through various phases of processing, to its final market destination, and it includes its disposal after use. For instance, agro-food value chains encompass activities that take place at the farm or rural level, including input supply, and continue through handling, processing, storage, packaging, and distribution. As products move successively through the various stages, transactions take place between multiple chain stakeholders, money changes hands, information is exchanged, and value is progressively added. Value chain participants sometimes cooperate to improve the overall competitiveness of the final product, but may also be completely unaware of the linkages between their operation and other upstream or downstream participants (Karl, Baker, Negassa, & Brent, 2009) Karl, M. R., Baker, D., Negassa, A., & Brent, R. R. (2009, August 16–22). *Concepts, applications, and extensions of value chain analysis to livestock systems in developing countries*. Contributed paper prepared for presentation at the International Association of Agricultural Economists Conference, Beijing. [Google Scholar]). Value chains, therefore, encompass all of the factors of production including land, labor, capital, technology, and inputs as well as all economic activities using input supply, production, transformation, handling, transport, marketing, and distribution necessary to create, sell, and deliver a product to a certain destination. By revealing strengths and weaknesses, VCA helps identify possible corrective measures (United Nations Industrial Development Organization, 2009) United Nations Industrial Development Organization. (2009). *Agro-value chain analysis and development* (The UNIDO Approach, A Staff Working Paper). Vienna. [Google Scholar]).

The valuhain approach, by its conceptualization, provides an indicative picture of underlying costs, profits, and trade competitiveness of various crops at a particular point in time (Karl et al., 2009) Karl, M. R., Baker, D., Negassa, A., & Brent, R. R. (2009, August 16–22). *Concepts, applications, and extensions of value chain analysis to livestock systems in developing countries*. Contributed paper prepared for presentation at the International Association of Agricultural Economists Conference, Beijing. [Google Scholar]). The competitiveness is measured against a defined benchmark at a particular point in time. The results make sense only when defined within the specific context, both in terms of space and time. The analysis does not capture the variations existing among individual producers, local traders, and processors who have their own cost structures that may vary significantly from the estimates used for this study. It is also worth noting that it was not possible to get relevant input from a wide range of stakeholders. As such, the results may only be indicative of major trends, without the accuracy required to define specific cost structures associated with the majority of players in the value-chains. The analysis does not also take into account seasonal variations in crop yield, price, and market opportunities. As such, the results of the analysis should be interpreted with caution as they only provide indicative trade-offs associated with different investment decisions and policy mechanisms aimed at enhancing smallholder agricultural competitiveness in the three countries.

Data Collection Methodology

The study carries out in Madhiji District Shikarpur. This survey was conducted using a questionnaire, where 60 household heads and 300 customers were sampled and interviewed, the main Objectives of study was to Specifically, this study focused on the impact of training provided to farmers on their perceived knowledge, acquisition of skills and adoption level of value added practices.

April 30, 2019

Results

Table 1: Demographic profile of the participants District Shikarpur

Demographic profile	Male	Female	Percentage
Gender	180		90
		20	10
Education Level			
Primary	160		80
		10	05
Seconadary	150	75	
		5	2.5
Graduate	40		20
		F-2	F 1
Post Graduate	01	0	0.1
Family Income	Up to 50,000	<100,000	
	120		60
		80	40
Value addition Knowledge	Low	Moderate	
	120		60
		80	40

Table 2: Reliability values of the scales developed for the study

Scales developed	Scale items	Scale range	Min. score	Max. score	Cronbach's alpha
Quality	10	1- 5	10	50	0.81
Taste	10	1-5	10	50	0.80
Adoption	15	0-2	0	30	0.78

Table; 3 Customer response on Value addition products of Tomato and Onion

Statement	V K		M K		SwK		NK		NaaK	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Percentage	Percentage	Percentage	Percentage	Percentage	Percentage
Value added tomato food items viz. jam, chutney, etc.	0	36	60	2	2	3.3	0.61			
Knowledge of value added balanced food	10	36	32	18	4	3.3	1.01			
Role of self help groups in creating awareness	24	2	54	20	0	3.3	1.05			
Value addition in ragi bakery food items	0	24	56	18	2	3.02	0.71			
Importance of value addition	14	16	36	32	12	3.08	1.06			
Value added income generating activities	2	14	58	26	0	2.92	0.69			
Economics of production costs involve in value added products	0	12	68	20	0	2.92	0.56			
Importance of packaging of value added food items	2	24	32	42	0	2.86	0.85			

Note VK= Very Knowledgeable; MK= Moderate Knowledgeable; SwK= Somewhat Knowledgeable; NK= Not Knowledgeable; NaaK = Not at all Knowledgeable.

Conclusions

The specific VCA we have done starts with the input supply level, then farm production and assembly. Due to data limitations, we have not considered the processing and distribution stages. At every stage, the analysis is based on enterprise budgets for the most typical crop production models and assembly transactions for each commodity up to the point where total accumulated value can most realistically be compared with an import or export parity price as a final measure of trade competitiveness. By identifying the types of costs that account for the majority of total value and where these costs occur, the approach is designed to help stakeholders focus on critical areas where attention is required to overall competitiveness along the value chain.

References

- i. 2006. *Value-added agriculture: from our futures on the table*, A Publication of ATTRA- National Sustainable Agriculture Information Service.
- ii. Lee, J.H., D. Henneberr and D. Pyles, 1991. *An analysis of value-added agricultural exports to middle-income developing countries: the case of wheat and beef products*, *Southern Journal of Agricultural Economics*, Dec. 1991.
- iii. Volkmer, Harold, L., M. Macdonald and C. Curtter, 1998. *The United States department of agriculture national commission on small farms: a report of the USDA National Commission on Small Farms*. Washington.
- iv. Gandhi, V., G. Kumar and R. Marsh, 2001. *Agro-industry for rural and small farmer development: issues and lessons from India*. *International Food and Agribusiness Management Review*, 2: 331-344.
- v. Reardon, T. and C.B. Barrett, 2000. *Agro-industrialization, globalization and international development: An overview of issues, patterns and determinants*. *Agricultural Economics*, 23: 195-205.
- vi. World Bank, 2003. *Reaching the rural poor- a renewed strategy for rural development*, Report No. 26763, Washington, DC.
- vii. Ali, N., 2004. *Rural development in India through post-harvest technology and value addition activities in the agricultural production catchment*. Paper presented at the *International Conference on Emerging Technologies in Agricultural and Food Engineering to be Held at IIT, Kharagpur, India*.
- viii. Anonymous, 2005. *Promoting value-adding in Nigerian agriculture: the cassava industry example*, Policy Brief No. 3. Technical assistance to the House of Representatives Committee on Agriculture, Nigeria.
- ix. Gulati, A., N. Minot, C. Delgado and S. Bora, 2005. *Growth in high-value agriculture in Asia and the emergence of vertical links with farmers*, Paper presented at the workshop "Linking Small-Scale Producers to Markets: Old and New Challenges" The World Bank.
- x. Evans, E., 2006 *Value added agriculture: is it right for me?* EDIS document FE638. Florida Cooperative Extension Service, Institute of Food and Agricultural Sciences, University of Florida, Gainesville.
- xi. Singh, R.B., P. Kumar and T. Woodhead, 2002. *Smallholder farmers in India: food security and agricultural policy*, FAO of the United Nations, Regional Office for Asia and the Pacific Bangkok, Thailand.
- xii. Mrema, G.C. and R.S. Rolle, 2002. *Status of the postharvest sector and its contribution to agricultural development and economic growth*. In: Mori, Y. Hayashi, T. & Highley, E. (Eds), *Value- Addition to Agricultural Products- Towards increase of farmers' income and vitalization of rural economy*. Proceedings of the 9th JIRCAS International Symposium, Tsukuba, Japan, 16-17 October, pp: 13-20.
- xiii. *Progressive Farmer*, 2000. *Value-added concept helps farmers*. Birmingham, AL: Progressive Farmer.
- xiv. Danielson, R. and D. Park, 2001. *Value-added, on-farm processing*, Case Study 11, North Dakota State University, USA. 16. NAAS (National Academy of Agricultural Sciences),

April 30, 2019

- xv. 2005. *Redefining agricultural education and extension system in changed scenario. Policy Paper No. 31, NAAS, New Delhi, India.*
- xvi. *World Appl. Sci. J., 22 (10): 1401-1411, 2013 1409*
- xvii. NAAS, 2006. *Employment opportunities in farm and non-farm sectors through technological interventions with emphasis on primary value addition. Policy Paper No. 37, New Delhi, India.*
- xviii. Sulaiman, R.V., T. Jafry and M.S. Asok, 2003. *Cafeteria for women in agriculture, NCAP Working Paper No.4, National Centre for Agricultural Economics and Policy Research, New Delhi, India.*
- xix. NCAP (National Centre for Agricultural Economics and Policy Research), 2005. *Impact of agricultural research: post-green revolution evidence from India, (Eds. P K Joshi, Suresh Pal, P S Birthal and M C S Bantilan), New Delhi, India.*
- xx. Deshpande, C.S., 2005. *Contracting framing as means of value-added agriculture, Occasional paper 40, Department of Economic Analysis and Research, National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development, Mumbai.*
- xxi. Anonymous, 2006. *Indian agriculture. Indo-Italian chamber of commerce and industry. The Government of India.*
- xxii. Government of India, 2005. *Food Processing Policy 2005, Ministry food processing industries, Government of India, New Delhi, India.*
- xxiii. World Bank, 2004. *World development indicators. CD-ROM database. The World Bank. Washington, DC.*
- xxiv. Amanor-Boadu, V ., 2004 *Strategic thinking for agricultural value-added businesses, The Kansas Ag Innovation Center, Department of Agricultural Economics, Kansas State University, USA.*
- xxv. CII-McKinsey and Cooperation Limited, 1997. London, UK.
- xxvi. George, D. and P. Mallery, 2003. *SPSS for windows step by step: a simple guide and Reference. pp: 11. Update. Fourth Edition. Boston, MA: Allyn & Bacon.*
- xxvii. *Karnataka Agricultural Policy, 2006 Agricultural Ministry, Government of Karnataka, India.*
- xxviii. Gill, K.K., 2001. *Diversification of agriculture and women's employment in Punjab. The Indian Journal of Labour Economics, 44: 259-267.*
- xxix. Singh, S., 2003. *Contract farming in India: Impacts on women and children." Gatekeeper Series pp: 111. London: IIED.*
- xxx. Patil, B.R., 2006. *Enhancement of extension systems in agriculture, Report of the APO Seminar on Enhancement of Extension Systems in Agriculture held in Pakistan, pp: 15-20.*